

CYBER CRIMES: AN ANALYSIS OF THE MAIN CRIMES AND THE BRAZILIAN CRIMINAL LEGISLATION

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Abstract: The internet has a very important role in the globalized world, it has brought benefits, such as: the expansion of communication frontiers, data storage and the facilitation of certain activities, but it has also contributed to the emergence of new crimes, which become known as “cyber crimes”. Thus, the number of virtual crimes against the population has increased significantly and in order to control these new illegal conducts, it was necessary to adapt the law to technological changes. However, this article deals with the most frequent cyber crimes in Brazil, how the criminal process works, the restrictions in combating these crimes and how to prevent them.

Keywords: Cyber crimes, internet, legislation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Internet arrived in Brazil in 1988 at the initiative of FAPESP - Research Support Foundation of the State of São Paulo and the LNCC (National Laboratory of Scientific Computing). And soon it became one of the countries with the greatest network coverage. Thus, the internet has become an extremely important tool in the globalized world, as it has revolutionized our form of communication, social and market relations. It brought numerous

benefits such as: easy access to knowledge and exchange of information, collaboration between people and organizations and social inclusion.

But there are not only benefits, the internet has directly intervened in the emergence of new types of crimes, the so-called virtual crimes. As a result, there had to be an adaptation of the right to the new reality to defend legal interests and preserve human dignity.

Intending to adjust the law to technological changes, Law 12,737/2012, known as the Carolina Dieckmann Law, was enacted, which “provides for the criminal classification of computer crimes; amends Decree-Law No. 2,848, of December 7, 1940 – Penal Code; and takes other measures”, with the aim of making up for the lack of specific legislation on the subject, which provides strong elements for the eradication of crimes of this nature.

Law 12.737/2012 emerged after the scandalous event that victimized global actress Carolina Dieckmann in 2012. And it was extremely important because it came to guarantee more dignity to internet users, valuing people's privacy, honor and intimacy.

In view of this, this article aims to address the concept of virtual crimes in Brazil, those that occur most frequently in the country, how the criminal prosecution of such crimes takes place, what are the restrictions in combating them and show some measures that help prevent them.

2. CYBER CRIMES

2.1. CYBER CRIME CONCEPT

Cyber crimes can also be known as: internet crimes, computer crimes, digital crimes, electronic crimes, cybercrimes, etc. It is the practice of any illegal conduct through electronic equipment (computers, *notebooks* , cell phones, etc.)

Fabrizio Rosa conceptualizes computer crime as being (ROSA, 2002):

“Conduct that violates the natural state of the data and resources offered by a data processing system, whether by compiling, storing or transmitting data, in its form, understood by the elements that make up a data processing, transmission or storage system , that is, still, in the most rudimentary form; 2. 'Computer Crime' is any procedure that attempts against data, which is done in the form in which they are stored, compiled, transferable or in transmission; 3. Thus, the 'Computer Crime' presupposes two indissoluble elements: against the data that are prepared for computer operations and, also, through the computer, using software and hardware, to perpetuate them; 4. The expression computer crimes, understood as such, is every typical, anti-legal and culpable action, against or through the use of automatic and/or electronic data processing or its transmission; 5. In computer crimes, the typical action is carried out against or

through the use of automatic data processing or its transmission. That is, the use of a computer system to attack a legally protected good or interest, belongs to the economic order, bodily integrity, individual freedom, privacy, honor, public or private property, Public Administration, etc. .”

It is still possible to classify cybercrimes as proper and improper. The proper ones are those that can only be practiced by computer means, actions such as invading systems, altering, stealing or inserting false data, that is, those that directly interfere with the software or hardware of the computer, while the improper ones can be carried out in any way. Anyway, electronics are just another new means of execution.

2.2. MAIN CYBER CRIMES IN BRAZIL

Among the main cyber crimes, according to a survey carried out in 2018 by the *Safernet website* Brasil em parceria com o Ministério Público Federal (MPF), estão: Pornografia infantil, apologia e incitação a crimes contra a vida, violência contra mulheres/misoginia, xenofobia (principalmente contra nordestinos), racismo, LGBTfobia, neonazismo, maus-tratos contra animais, intolerância religiosa, tráfico de pessoas. Dos crimes citados acima, serão descritos alguns a seguir.

Child pornography is characterized by producing, acquiring, selling or publishing photographs, videos or other sexually explicit or pornographic images involving children or adolescents, or any representation of their sexual organs for sexual or pornographic purposes.

The Brazilian legislation in force characterizes as a crime the conduct of "Presenting, producing, selling, supplying, disclosing or publishing, by any means of communication, including the Internet, photographs or images with pornography or explicit sex scenes involving children or adolescents" (Art. 241 of the Child and Adolescent Statute).

Racism is discrimination that is related to the physical characteristics that determine your race, that declare prejudice, coercion, aggression, exposure, that suffers different treatment or interferes with your economic and social opportunities.

The Federal Constitution of 1988 determines, in Art. 3, item XLI, that "The fundamental objectives of the Federative Republic of Brazil are: to promote the good of all, without prejudice as to origin, race, sex, color, age and any other forms of discrimination"; and in Article 5, item XLI , that "the law shall punish any discrimination that violates fundamental rights and freedoms".

Homophobia can be defined as discrimination, intolerance, or any manifestation of repudiation, such as irrepressible aversion, repugnance, fear, hatred, prejudice against homosexuals, lesbians, bisexuals and transsexuals (known as LGBT), and homoaffection.

The Brazilian Federal Constitution still does not mention homophobia directly as a crime. But the practice of homophobia is a crime and is present in Art. 3, item XLI that "The fundamental objectives of the Federative Republic of Brazil are: to promote the good of all, without prejudice of origin, race, sex, color, age and any other forms of discrimination; and in Art. 5, item XLI, which "the law shall punish any discrimination that violates fundamental rights and freedoms".

2.3. CRIMINAL PROCESS IN VIRTUAL CRIMES AND ITS RESTRICTIONS

Law is associated with jurisdiction, it works as a system of rules that establish order in all areas of social relations, regulate human conduct and conflict resolution. Dealing with virtual crimes, they are the crimes committed in the virtual environment that can be framed in the Brazilian Penal Code, and the offenders are subject to penalties provided for in the Law.

Brazil does not have legislation that covers all types of cyber crimes that may occur. In this case, with the absence of specific legislation, the person who committed a crime through the internet must be judged by the Penal Code itself, respecting the necessary differences.

A crucial point in the advancement of legislation in relation to cyber crimes was what happened to global actress Carolina Dieckmann, who had her personal computer invaded and several intimate photos of the actress were stolen, they began to extort her, requesting money in exchange for not disclosing her content on the internet. Violators were punished for theft, extortion and defamation, but not for the crime of computer hacking.

As a result, Bill No. 2,793, which was already under discussion in the National Congress, was processed on an urgent basis, and was enacted in record time. And due to the repercussion it took, it became known as the "Carolina Dieckmann Law".

Law 12,737/2012, known as the Carolina Dieckmann Law, which "deals with the criminal classification of computer crimes; amends Decree-Law No. 2,848, of December 7, 1940 – Penal Code; and takes other measures. It cites the following articles:

"Invasion of computer device

Art. 154-A. Invading someone else's computer device, whether or not connected to the computer network, through undue violation of a security mechanism and with the aim of obtaining, tampering with or destroying data or information without the express or tacit authorization of the device owner or installing vulnerabilities to obtain an illicit advantage:

Penalty - detention, from 3 (three) months to 1 (one) year, and a fine.

§ 1 The same penalty applies to anyone who produces, offers, distributes, sells or disseminates a computer device or program with the aim of allowing the practice of the conduct defined in the caput.

§ 2 The penalty is increased by one-sixth to one-third if the invasion results in economic loss.

§ 3 If the invasion results in obtaining content of private electronic communications, commercial or industrial secrets, confidential information, as defined by law, or unauthorized remote control of the invaded device:

Penalty - imprisonment, from 6 (six) months to 2 (two) years, and a fine, if the conduct does not constitute a more serious crime.

§ 4 In the case of § 3, the penalty is increased by one to two thirds if there is disclosure, commercialization or transmission to a third party, in any capacity, of the data or information obtained.

§ 5 The penalty is increased from one third to one half if the crime is committed against:

I - President of the Republic, governors and mayors;

II - President of the Federal Supreme Court;

III - President of the Chamber of Deputies, of the Federal Senate, of the State Legislative Assembly, of the Legislative Chamber of the Federal District or of the Municipal Chamber; or

IV - Head of direct and indirect federal, state, municipal or Federal District administration.”

“criminal action

Art. 154-B. In the crimes defined in art. 154-A, only proceeds through representation, unless the crime is committed against the direct or indirect public administration of any of the Powers of the Union, States, Federal District or Municipalities or against public service concessionaires.”

Art. 3rd Art. 266 and 298 of Decree-Law No. 2,848, of December 7, 1940 - Code

Penal Code, shall come into force with the following wording:

“Interruption or disruption of telegraphic, telephone, computer, telematic service or public utility information

Art. 266.

§ 1º Incurs the same penalty who interrupts the telematic or information service of public utility, or prevents or hinders its restoration.

§ 2 Double penalties apply if the crime is committed on the occasion of calamity public.” (NR)

“Forgery of private document

Art. 298.

card forgery

Single paragraph. For the purposes of the provisions of the caput, it is equivalent to a private document the

credit or debit card.” (NR)

After the law was enacted, it was heavily criticized by security professionals. of information and legal doctrine, as it presents very broad precepts that can generate doubts and subjective interpretations, which can be used against the victim in a supposed defense of an accused of a cyber crime. In addition, there is no punishment for distributing images, nor for breaking into computers.

In addition to this, since there is no Legislation on online purchases and sales, that is, internet purchases, to integrate the gaps in the Consumer Protection Code regarding electronic commerce, Federal Decree 7962/13 came into force.

2.4. HOW TO PREVENT CYBER CRIMES

With the countless cases of virtual crimes that happen in Brazil, it is necessary to look for ways to prevent them. One of the first measures is to be suspicious of things out of the ordinary, not to click or open links or files from dubious sources, to have a good antivirus, preferably a paid one, and not to use computers other than personal ones to carry out financial transactions.

These are some active measures, but there are preventive measures that can be taken to protect people from possible risks to cybercrime, which are as follows:

- Constant updating of the operating system is extremely important, as malicious software uses the vulnerability of outdated systems. The objective is to choose the best one and always keep it up to date, since currently the systems are very complete, they come with *antivirus*, *firewall*, *antiphishing* and etc.
- Use a full-service security suite to ensure protection against viruses and Internet threats.
- Use strong passwords that are not related to personal data, do not repeat passwords on different sites, always change them and use the password management application that helps protect them.
- Always keep private personal information blocked, on social media.
- Protect the home network with an encrypted password and a VPN, which will encrypt the traffic leaving the devices until it arrives at the destination, preventing a *hacker*, for example, from interception.

- Make regular *backups* , turn off voice activated devices, cover *webcams* when not in use, clear browser history and *cookies* , etc.

Measures that can be taken by the population to increase internet security and prevent cybercrime were presented. And if a cybercrime occurs, it is important to report it to the responsible authorities to prevent the same from happening to other people in the future.

3. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

As previously presented, the internet has brought many benefits, whether in the political, economic, social or cultural areas. But with it came new types of crimes, called cyber crimes, such as: child pornography, the practice of racism and homophobia, theft of data through computers, among other crimes.

As a result, there was a need for the law to adapt to the changes brought about by technological advances, aiming to overcome the lack of specific legislation on the subject.

To combat these crimes, Law 12.737/2012 (Carolina Dieckmann Law) was enacted, but one of the main obstacles is the lack of specific rules for the regulation of virtual crimes, which is why numerous behaviors are not properly penalized. The current legislation manages to control some of these crimes, but others still need bills.

The elaboration of a norm is not enough in the fight against these crimes. And that although there are preventive measures that can be taken to avoid some types of cybercrime, it is still not enough. It is still necessary to encourage the population's awareness, implement the theme in schools, educate children and adolescents to avoid illicit practices on the internet.

It is concluded that the Legislation, even in increasing evolution, is still flawed in the fight against virtual crime, mainly in the clarity and application of its Laws, and that virtual crimes tend to grow, since technology advances every day, so the Legislation has to adapt to this reality, in a proportional way.

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